

Studies in the effect of light on trimethoprim, furosemide and metoclopramide

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Abstract : Photolysis of trimethoprim, furosemide and metoclopramide under 60 W and 200 W tungsten lamp and 125 W and 250 W mercury vapour lamp in different conditions like different pH (acidic, neutral, alkaline) and different phases (solid and liquid) gave different products. Structures of these products have been established by spectral and elemental analysis.

Keywords : Photolysis, trimethoprim, furosemide, metoclopramide, tungsten lamp, mercury vapour lamp.

Introduction

Photochemistry of organic compounds has been a vast field of research since a long time. Almost all types of compounds have been studied so far¹⁻¹⁰. The effect of various parameters like wavelength, intensity, nature of solvent, pH, etc., have been also studied¹¹⁻²⁰. A thorough survey of the literature shows that no work has been done on the effect of light on trimethoprim, furosemide and metoclopramide which are medicinally important compounds. So these compounds were chosen for the present study.

Trimethoprim is a broad-spectrum antimicrobial agent used extensively worldwide alone or in combination with sulfamethoxazole for the treatment of enteric, respiratory, skin and urinary track infections²¹. The furosemide is a powerful diuretic. It is used to treat excessive fluid accumulation and swelling (edema) of the body caused by heart failure, cirrhosis, chronic kidney failure and nephritic syndrome²². The metoclopramide is antiemetic and is used to control vomiting. The polyacrylate based micro particles are used for sustained release of metoclopramide in human body²³.

Experimental

Photochemical reactions of trimethoprim, furosemide and metoclopramide under UV and visible light :

The substrate (2 g) was dissolved in methanol (200 ml). Few drops of HCl (1 N) and ethanolic sodium hydroxide solution (1 N) were used to make medium acidic

and alkaline respectively. The solution was irradiated by low (125 W) and high (250 W) intensity UV source and tungsten lamp (for visible light) in neutral, acidic and alkaline medium respectively in photo reactor for appropriate time (Table 1). The progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC. The products were separated by preparative TLC using methanol : benzene (8 : 2) solvent system and were recrystallized from methanol. Under visible light, no change in TLC was observed even after prolonged irradiation.

Solid phase photolysis of trimethoprim, furosemide and metoclopramide :

Slurry of the substrate (2 g) was prepared with silica gel in distilled water and then spread over a glass plate as a thin coat. The plate was dried at room temperature and then was irradiated under UV lamp and sun. The progress of the reaction was monitored by scratching a small amount of silica gel from the plate and then mixing with solvent which was spotted on the plate for TLC. No change was observed even after 70 h of irradiation so the irradiation was stopped.

Results and discussion

Trimethoprim was found to be photo reactive only in acidic condition under low intensity UV source and it gave the product **1** by deamination as represented in Scheme 1. The IR spectrum of product **1** shows peaks at 2853.72, 2932.06 cm⁻¹ (aliphatic C-H stretch) and 1614.14, 1503.92, 1461.79 cm⁻¹ (aromatic C=C ring stretch). The ¹H NMR gives signals at δ 6.8 (aromatic

Table 1. The products obtained by the UV photolysis of trimethoprim, furosemide and metoclopramide

Substrate	Product	Intensity	Medium	Reaction time (h)	Yield (g)	M.p (°C)
Trimethoprim	1	Low	Acidic	37	0.4	160
		Low	Neutral	N.R		
		Low	Alkaline	N.R		
	2	High	Neutral	35	0.8	120
		High	Acidic	29	1.1	160
	3	High	Alkaline	33	0.9	240
Furosemide		Low/High	Alkaline/Acidic/Neutral	N.R		
Metoclopramide	5	Low	Neutral	N.R		
	6	Low	Acidic	40	0.5	120
		Low	Alkaline	N.R		
	7, 8	High	Neutral	36	0.8, 0.5	160, V.L
	6	High	Acidic	26	1.0	120
		High	Alkaline	N.R		

Note : N.R - No Reaction and V.L - Viscous liquid.

protons ring B), 7.0–8.2 (aromatic protons ring A), 3.6–3.8 (OCH₃ protons), 1.9 (CH₂ protons). The ¹³C NMR gives signals at δ 154–165 (aromatic carbon atoms ring A), 126–137 (aromatic carbon atoms ring B), 35 (CH₂ carbon atom), 56 (OCH₃ carbon atoms). The mass spectrum gives the molecular ion peak at *m/z* 260, base peak is observed at *m/z* 181. Found : C, 64.72; H, 6.19; N, 10.83. Calcd. for C₁₄H₁₆O₃N₂ : C, 64.62; H, 6.15; N, 10.77%.

Irradiation of trimethoprim under high intensity UV source, gave different products in different media. In neutral medium it gave the product **2** by the attack of aerial oxygen as represented in Scheme 2. The IR spectrum of product **2** shows peaks at 3319.32, 3470.12 (N–H stretch), 3014.04 (aromatic C–H stretch), 2950.81 (aliphatic C–H stretch), 1654.71 (C=O stretch) and 1595.92, 1508.21, 1467.67 cm⁻¹ (aromatic C=C ring stretch). The ¹H NMR gives signals at δ 7.8 (aromatic proton ring A), 6.4 (aromatic protons ring B), 4.6, 4.8 (NH₂ protons), 3.8 (OCH₃ protons). The ¹³C NMR gives signals at δ 175 (C=O carbon), 150–165 (aromatic carbons ring A), 127–135 (aromatic carbons ring B), 55 (OCH₃ carbon). The mass spectrum gives the molecular ion peak at *m/z* 304 and the base peak at *m/z* 195. Found : C, 55.30; H, 5.34; N, 18.56. Calcd. for C₁₄H₁₆N₄O₄ : C, 55.26; H, 5.26; N, 18.42%.

In acidic medium, it gave the product which was confirmed to be the same as **1** by Co-TLC and mixed melting point.

In alkaline medium, it gave the product **3** by dimerisation as represented in Scheme 3. The IR spectrum of product **3** shows peaks at 3684.42, 3396.21 (N–H stretch), 2932.06, 2853.72 (aliphatic C–H stretch), 1614.14, 1503.92, 1461.79 (aromatic C=C ring stretch) and 665.26 cm⁻¹ (aromatic ring bending). The ¹H NMR gives signals at δ 7.8 (aromatic protons, pyrimidine ring), 6.4 (aromatic protons, benzene ring), 4.6, 4.8 (NH₂ protons), 3.8 (OCH₃ protons), 1.6, 1.8 (C–H protons). The ¹³C NMR gives signals at δ 154–165 (aromatic carbon atoms, pyrimidine ring), 125–140 (aromatic carbon atoms, benzene ring), 34 (C–H carbon), 55 (OCH₃ carbon). The mass spectrum gives the molecular ion peak at *m/z* 578 and base peak at *m/z* 289. Found : C, 64.72; H, 6.19; N, 10.83. Calcd. for C₁₄H₁₆O₃N₂ : C, 64.62; H, 6.15; N, 10.77%.

Furosemide does not undergo any change even after prolonged irradiation in all the conditions. Metoclopramide was found to be photoreactive only in acidic medium under low intensity UV source and it gave the product **6** as represented in Scheme 4. The IR spectrum of product **6** shows peaks at 1656.65 (C=O stretch), 2926.64, 2853.78 (aliphatic C–H stretch), 1601.02, 1495.32, 1463.67 cm⁻¹ (aromatic C=C ring stretch) and 638.98 cm⁻¹ (C–Cl stretch). The ¹H NMR gives signals at δ 6.1–6.8 (aromatic protons), 5.7 (aromatic NH protons), 3.8 (OCH₃ protons), 3.0–3.6 (–CH₂ protons) and 1.2 (–CH₃ protons). The ¹³C NMR gives signals at δ 167 (carbonyl carbon atom), 130–159 (aromatic carbon atoms), 55

Reactions of trimethoprim

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

Scheme 3

Reactions of metoclopramide

Scheme 4

Scheme 5

(OCH₃ carbon), 10 (CH₃ carbon), 47-52 (CH₂ carbon). The mass spectrum gives the molecular ion peak and base peak at *m/z* 284. Found : C, 59.16; H, 7.45; N, 9.91; Cl,

12.39. Calcd. for C₁₄N₂N₂O₂Cl : C, 59.15; H, 7.39; N, 9.86, Cl, 12.32%.

Under high intensity UV source, metoclopramide gave

same products (**7** and **8**) in neutral and alkaline media by hydrogen abstraction from the solvent (Scheme 5). The product **8** has been confirmed by Co-TLC with authentic sample of diethyl amine. The IR spectrum of product **7** shows peaks at 3399.77, 3350.52 (N-H stretch), 2963.20 (aliphatic C-H stretch), 1672.73 (C=O stretch), 1592.21, 1492.94 (aromatic C=C ring stretch), 684.30 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl stretch). The ¹H NMR gives signals at δ 6.3, 7.6 (aromatic protons), 4.6 (NH₂ protons), 5.2 (NH proton), 3.7 (OCH₃ protons), 3.6 (-CH₂ protons). The ¹³C NMR gives signals at δ 167 (carbonyl carbon atom), 132–158 (aromatic carbon atoms), 55 (OCH₃ carbon atoms), 35 (CH₂ carbon atom), 8 (CH₃ carbon atom). The mass spectrum gives the molecular ion peak at *m/z* 228 and base peak at *m/z* 199. For product **7**, Found : C, 52.69; H, 5.73; N, 12.33; Cl, 15.35. Calcd. for C₁₀H₁₃N₂O₂Cl : C, 52.63; H, 5.70; N, 12.28; Cl, 15.35%.

In acidic condition, it gave the product which was found be the same as **6** by Co-TLC and mixed melting point.

Conclusion :

Trimethoprim and metoclopramide which are in use as medicines are photochemically active. The intensity of the source and the pH of the reaction medium affect the course of reaction. Higher intensity source gives greater yields of the products indicating that the dissociation of the compound is more. The pH affects the course of reaction giving different products. However furosemide is stable under all the conditions.

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References

1. M. Sergio Bonesi, K. Laura Crevatin and Rosa Erra-Balsells, *Photochem. Photobiol. Sci.*, 2004, **3**, 381.
2. Javier Catalan, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 2007, **111**, 8774.
3. L. Anne Boreen, A. William Arnold and Kristopher Mcneill, *Environ. Sci. Technol.*, 2004, **38**, 3933.
4. M. F. Semmelhack, Steve Kunkes and S. Carol Lee, *J. Chem. Soc. (D)*, 1971, 698.
5. N. Bosaric, M. Horvat, K. Mlinaric-Majerski, E. Zimmermann and A. G. Newdorfi Griesbeck, *Org. Lett.*, 2008, **10**, 3965.
6. Q. Liu, H. H. Liyn, B. Zhang, C. H. Chen, L. Z. Tung and Wu, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2011, **76**, 1444.
7. G. Kaupp, *Journal of Microscopy*, 1994, **174**, 15.
8. C. Emil Burciana, Violeta Melinte, Tinea Buruiana, C. Bogdan Simionescu, Thomas Lippert and Lukas Urech, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. (A)*, 2007, **186**, 270.
9. Ming-Der Su, *J. Phys. Chem. (A)*, 2008, **112**, 10420.
10. J. M. Menter, R. E. Hurst and S. S. West, *Photochemistry and Photobiology*, 1979, **29**, 473.
11. Shubha Jain, Shivraj Singh Chawada and Suresh C. Ameta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **81**, 965.
12. G. Oster, M. Goodman and L. Citrarel, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **84**, 703.
13. Shubha Jain and M. M. Bokadia, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1999, **38**, 232.
14. A. J. Butcher, H. R. Hinz (Jr.), N. Tsou and S. Shah, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1984, **48**, 5483.
15. Shubha Jain, Rajbala Pandey and Binitha Kheradia, *Asian J. Chem.*, 2005, **17**, 1295.
16. K. C. Kwang, N. J. Turro and H. D. Roth, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1994, **59**, 1102.
17. E. R. Cole, G. Crank and E. Lye, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1978, **31**, 2675.
18. Shubha Jain, Amitbodh Upadhyaya and Binitha Kheradia, *Int. J. Chem. Sci.*, 2003, **1**, 107.
19. F. R. Stemitz, Pua and H. Vyas, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1968, **33**, 1136.
20. Shubha Jain and Shivraj Singh Chawada, *Asian J. Chem.*, 2001, **13**, 1231.
21. P. L. Huovinen, Sundstom, G. Swedberg and O. Skold, *Antimicrob. Agents Chemother.*, 1995, **39**, 279.
22. C. B. Brown, C. S. Ogg and J. S. Cameron, *Clin. Nephrol.*, 1981, **15**, 90.
23. A. Ganza-Gonzalez, S. Anguiano-Igea, F. J. Othero-Espinor, P. J. Blanco-Mendez and Buri, *S.T.P. Pharma Sciences*, 2002, **12**, 103.